

Nanoindentation Behaviour of Mg Based Hybrid Composites with Graphite nanofiber/Alumina Fiber

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SUMMARY

Nanoindentation was performed on Mg based hybrid composites using continuous stiffness method with an indentation depth of about 2000 nm. In order to find out the modulus and hardness of the composites at local regions, nanoindentation tests were performed in different locations of the sample. They have been found to be higher than those of Mg alloy. This can be attributed primarily to a higher constraint to the localized matrix deformation during indentation due to the presence of GNFs and $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_{3\text{sf}}$. The enhancement of indentation properties of composites is also due to the presence of MgO and $\text{Mg}_{17}\text{Al}_{12}$ precipitates.

Keywords: Nanoindentation, Mg MMCs, mechanical properties

INTRODUCTION

There is a growing interest to evaluate the mechanical properties of MMCs, using the nanoindentation method [1-4]. Since the width of reinforcement-matrix interface and the interfibre distance is of the order of micrometers, it is practically not possible to determine the mechanical properties around the reinforcement region using conventional techniques. However, nanoindentation which measures the resistance to plastic deformation in small volumes is ideal in such cases. Nanoindentation is simply an indentation test in which the length scale of penetration is measured in nanometers (10^{-9}) rather than in microns (10^{-6}). Apart from the displacement scale involved, the distinguishing feature of most nanoindentation testing is the indirect measurement of the contact area. In conventional indentation tests, the area of contact is calculated from direct measurements of the dimensions of the residual impression left in the specimen surface upon the removal of load. The force involved is usually in the milli-newton range and is measured with a resolution of nano-newtons. The depth of penetration is in the order of microns with a resolution of less than a nanometer.

Nanoindentation is generally performed by using an MTS Nanoindenter-XP. In this, nanoindentation the surface of the material is indented by a hard tip with known properties (usually made of diamond). Normally, the indenter used is Berkovich diamond three sided pyramid with a face angle of 65.3° . Indentation tests are usually preformed by bringing the indenter in contact with the surface of the specimen with a controlled load and then measuring the resulting depth of penetration. The route used for evaluating the hardness and elastic modulus by nanoindentation method was continuous stiffness measurement (CSM). In the present work, nanoindentation was performed on Mg (AM50) based GNF/ $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_{3\text{sf}}$ hybrid MMCs containing 10

vol.% of fibres. The hardness and elastic modulus have been evaluated using continuous stiffness measurement (CSM). The processing of Mg hybrid MMCs can be seen elsewhere [5].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fig.1 (a) shows the load displacement curves for both the Mg matrix and near the interface of GNFs and $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_{3\text{sf}}$ at 2000 nm depth of indentation, by CSM. The curves suggest that some structural changes may occur within the composites during the test. It is observed that when indentation on Mg matrix closer to the interface of GNFs and $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_{3\text{sf}}$ is done, the displacement is lower compared to the indentation on Mg matrix region away from the reinforcements. The loading curve for Mg matrix was more irregular than that of the other regions due to the presence of MgO and $\text{Mg}_{17}\text{Al}_{12}$ precipitates. This might be due to the dislocation slip or twinning, and phase transformation during indentation [6]. The displacement is higher for the indentation on Mg matrix away from the reinforcements region. It can be seen that curve is irregular; either as a result of the indentations in matrix material with fibres near the surface, indentation on GNF edges whereby the indenter slides off or the surface roughness of the sample. AFM image after nanoindentation test is shown in Fig.1 (b). As can be seen from the AFM image and the scanned surface profile, the indentation depth was slightly higher than those for the Al hybrid MMCs and the pile up could not be observed.

Fig.1 (a) Indentation load displacement curves by CSM; indentation depth of 2000 nm
(b) AFM image of nanoindentation mark.

Fig.2 (a, b) show the indentation modulus and hardness values for the indentation on Mg matrix, which is close to the interface of GNFs and $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_{3\text{sf}}$. Initially, the modulus and hardness are increased with a smaller indentation depth probably due the indentation size effect. In the most of cases in the early stages of indentation, there was some scatter in the measured values; the roughness of Mg surface might have contributed to this scatter, as documented by Bouzakis et al [7]. The average modulus and hardness were 80 and 6 GPa respectively. The modulus and

hardness have been found to be higher than those of magnesium alloy ((Fig.3 (a, b)). This can be attributed primarily to a higher constraint to the localized matrix deformation during indentation due to the presence of reinforcements. However, the values are reduced with an increase in the depth of penetration, which may be due to the slip between $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_{3\text{sf}}$ and GNFs when the indenter comes in contact with the reinforcements. Fig.4 (a, b) show the results of nanoindentation tests carried out near the $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_{3\text{sf}}$ region. The average modulus and hardness values were 60 and 1.8 GPa respectively. The enhancement in the indentation properties has been attributed to the $\text{Mg}_{17}\text{Al}_{12}$ precipitates. The $\text{Mg}_{17}\text{Al}_{12}$ precipitates formed in the matrix metal are hard and brittle [8]. Fig.5 (a, b) show the hardness and modulus values obtained from the indentation applied on GNFs cluster. Average modulus and hardness values were 38 and 0.8 GPa respectively. Due to the influence of nanopores within the GNFs cluster, the properties varied significantly with indentation depth.

Fig.2 Nanoindentation profiles observed by CSM at 2000 nm; indentation near the interface of GNFs and $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_{3\text{sf}}$ regions (a) Modulus, (b) Hardness.

(a)

(b)

Fig.3 Nanoindentation profiles observed by CSM at 2000 nm; indentation in Mg alloy (A356), (a) Modulus, (b) Hardness.

(a)

(b)

Fig.4 Nanoindentation profiles observed by CSM at 2000 nm; indentation of near the Al_2O_{3sf} regions (a) Modulus, (b) Hardness.

Fig.5 Nanoindentation profiles observed by CSM at 2000 nm; indentation in GNFs cluster (a) Modulus, (b) Hardness.

CONCLUSIONS

Nanoindentation is used to evaluate the elastic modulus and hardness of Mg based hybrid MMCs. The large number of dislocations in the plastic zone formed near the indented region of GNFs and $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_{3\text{sf}}$ contributes to an increase in modulus and hardness values. The indentation on Mg matrix closer to the GNFs and $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_{3\text{sf}}$ region with the presence of MgO gave the higher hardness and modulus values. The decrease in modulus and hardness has been attributed to the presence of nanopores within the GNFs cluster

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